

REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH AND RIGHTS OF WOMEN IN SAUDI ARABIA

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Abstract:

This study presents a cross-sectional analysis of reproductive health and rights among native Saudi and expatriate Indian women. The birth rate in Saudi Arabia is approximately 14.84 births per 1,000 people, and the total fertility rate is about 2.12 births per woman (Macrotrends, 2024a, 2024b). Life expectancy at birth is 75.6 years for males and 78.8 years for females (WHO, 2024). The Saudi native population consists of around 10.6 million males and 10.2 million females (Global Media Insight, 2024).

Reproductive health is a crucial determinant of women's overall well-being, affecting not only their physical health but also their social, cultural, and economic conditions. Reproductive health encompasses various factors such as medical care, socioeconomic status, cultural norms, religion, and education, all of which influence women's health. This paper explores the impact of these factors on the reproductive health of Saudi women and expatriate Indian women.

Keyword: Reproductive health, reproductive rights, Saudi women, expatriate women, socioeconomic factors, cultural impact, fertility rate.

1. Introduction

Reproductive health refers to a condition in which the reproductive process is accomplished in complete physical, mental and social well-being and is not merely the absence of any disease in the reproductive organs or the reproductive system. The World Health Organization, International Women's Health Movement groups and International Family Planning network, in contrast to bio-medical approaches to women's health, developed the concept of women's reproductive health. "Reproductive health, therefore, implies that people can have a

satisfying and safe sex life and that they can reproduce with the freedom to decide it, when and how often to do so" In other words, reproductive health implies that women can go safely through pregnancy and childbirth, that fertility regulations can be achieved without health hazards and that people are safe in having sex (WHO, 2011).

Reproductive change in developing countries" points out that the status of women as a crucial intervening factor between modernization and fertility decline has been widely debated. It is, after all, women who suffer the main burden of reproduction, and it is plausible to argue that they may see greater advantages in controlling fertility than their husbands. Several theorists have argued that strongly patrilineal societies where females are denied equal status with men in public or commercial life are more resistant to reproductive change than egalitarian societies.

The health care and services come under the Saudi Ministry of Health (MOH) . MOH is highly centralized, with limited powers over the regional directorates regarding financing, planning, and recruitment. The ministry provides free health care and services to all the natives and expats in the public sector. Of the total number of physicians and nurses, the contribution of Saudi nationals is just 17 per cent, and the rest are foreigners.

Saudi Arabia has a three-tier system in the public health sector. District-based Primary Health Centers (PHCs) provide essential health services. There are about 3300 of these across the country. Referrals are made to secondary care general hospitals or public hospitals. Tertiary care occurs when specialist hospitals, such as the King Faisal Specialty and Research Center, are required.

In Saudi Arabia - religious beliefs, cultural practices and traditions are the main factors that influence the health-seekers, and these health-seekers have a very rigid attitude towards their health needs.

There is a dearth of health education and a lack of basic preventive measures, which takes its toll on women's reproductive, sexual, and mental health. Some basic reproductive and sexual health care programs are in place, and health care education is being imparted but is inadequate. Preventive health care does not seem to be the priority of the health service planners. Socio-religious norms also guide health policy planners and health providers. Hence, the health equity of women suffers

greatly. The gender-biased system of Saudi Arabia blocks women in the field of health care from deciding their preferences, and their roles are very restricted. They are not given chances or encouraged to take up leadership positions. If this practice is undertaken, women in the position will have a say in healthcare policy-making from women's perspectives.

Legal restrictions also constrain women's access to health services. Other factors that influence women's attitude towards seeking health services are male guardianship, their socio-economic state and gender segregation. Saudi culture insists that women keep on giving birth till the very last of their age, hence increasing the risk of a child being born with inherited and genomic deformities. The family's prerequisite is always a boy child, and this requirement stems from the belief that a girl cannot carry on the family name. Girls are considered potential risks to the family's honour because any misbehavior from them will affect the family's name.

Late pregnancies also arise from the fear in women that if they stop giving birth, their husband might marry another woman, and therefore, the older woman wants to prove to her husband and his family that she is still young and fertile. Strict male guardianship is another obstacle towards women's health. A husband's consent is necessary if a woman needs medical care or advice; she cannot decide for herself. Despite recent developments and progress, this practice is still widely accepted in Saudi communities.

The Government has a premarital care policy in place, but the implementation of this policy is left to the prospective husband and wife. Premarital care is when medical and pathological tests are done on the prospective couples, and they are counselled accordingly. Screening procedures

These are done to look for any inherited diseases and abnormalities that might occur. So even if the screening results are against the would-be couple, the prevalent culture and tradition see no harm in such marriages. The premarital medical investigations also adhere to the Islamic code of Sharia because the Prophet Mohammad (PBUH) said: "Do not join the healthy and the sick." The Saudi Royal Cabinet has appropriately issued an order to make premarital examination mandatory in the Kingdom. The factors causing countries like Saudi Arabia to lag behind the international movement towards improved SRH can be

summarized in four main areas: religion, lack of services, lack of proper skills among health care providers, and the taboo surrounding this topic.

This paper is specifically about the reproductive health of women in Saudi Arabia. This study is divided into two parts: the first discusses Saudi women's health, and the second discusses expatriate women's health. This study also tried to determine the Government's role in providing maternal health facilities. Moreover, are these facilities offered equally to locals and expatriate women? It was also examined if the health facilities were accessible to the locals. All maternal health-related and emergency services are present at the centres, and do these services cater to basic health needs? The study looks into the Government's health education and health awareness programs. This paper broadly explores women's rights and tries to find its links with society's religion and other social and cultural norms. It also ponders the effects of these norms on the health accessibility of women and questions whether women are free to make autonomous decisions about their health. The health service provider's role is also analyzed.

Additionally, the paper defines the selected indicators as the age of marriage, polygamy, antenatal care, delivery practices, post-natal care, awareness of family planning methods, infant mortality rate, fertility rate, and reproductive rights.

2. Background and review of broad concepts

Sexual and reproductive health is an integral right of everyone to attain the highest standard of physical and mental health (Hunt & de Mesquita, 2006). The literature on the present study is reviewed on the following broad themes.

2.1. Age at marriage, education and infant mortality rate

Women's reproductive health in the Middle East: According to the Population Reference Bureau, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is a rapidly developing country with considerable economic and human resources. It is considered one of the wealthiest Arab countries in the Middle East. Saudi Arabia has a high rate of early marriages compared with other Arab countries. Saudi Arabia has no minimum legal age for marriage, and many girls are married as soon as they reach menarche, i.e., their first menstrual period (Rashad, Osman, & Roudi-Fahimi, n.d.)

The rate of early teenage marriage, which is defined as marriage under the age of 16 years, was found to be approximately 27.2 per cent in Jeddah (Shawky & Milaat, 2000). This practice, widespread throughout most Arab world, is related to traditional beliefs. Families prefer to marry their daughters early, with culture, traditional values, virginity and family honour being the main reasons (Rashad, Osman, & Roudi-Fahimi, n.d.).

Many factors influence women's health. The genetic constitution, exposure to disease-producing organisms, imbalanced or inadequate nutrition, and low resistance to infection determine health. In addition, social, cultural, economic, political and environmental factors, as well as the availability of health services, significantly influence the health of individuals. Attitudes to marriage, age at marriage, the value attached to fertility and the sex of the child, the pattern of family organization and the ideal role demanded of women by social conventions- are all cultural norms that affect women's health (Fazli, 2014).

2.2. Cultural practices related to Women's health

Some cultural factors that have a significant bearing on women's reproductive health in Saudi Arabia are recognized in the study. They wrote about the Obesity problem found in girls in Saudi Arabia as there is no sports education in girls' schools, and social norms prohibit females from practicing physical activities in public (Al-Nozha et al., 2005).

Lack of exercise is a known cause of obesity. It is not surprising, therefore, that the prevalence of obesity (body mass index > 30 kg/m²) for 30–70-year-old Saudi females was 44.0 per cent compared with only 26.4 per cent in males. When we compare this Prevalence of obesity in Sweden, in comparison the Prevalence of obesity for 25–64-year-old Swedes was 11.0 per cent for females and 14.8 per cent for males (Neovius, Janson, & Rossner, 2006) Health indicators 2005–2006, Ministry of Health of Saudi Arabia (2009) indicates that Saudi women cannot study engineering, law or journalism. According to the latest official figures, 49.9 per cent of the Saudi population is female. Out of that, barely 21 per cent of them contribute to social development (Vidyasagar & Rea, 2004) because it is socially unacceptable for women to work in fields other than teaching and medicine (Aldosari, 2017). In kinship societies, such as Saudi Arabia, the change in women's perceptions of gender roles with education and exposure increases the

tension surrounding the established gender norms and expectations (Boutayeb & Serghini, 2006).

2.3. Age at marriage and health issues

The infant mortality rate in Saudi Arabia was high in the early 1980s, with an estimated 118 deaths per 1000 live births (World Health Organization [WHO], 2006). The Work of WHO Annual Report (2009) describes that, by contrast, based only on deliveries of infants in hospitals of the MOH, the infant mortality rate was 18.6 per 1000 in 2006 (Ministry of Health of Saudi Arabia, 2009). According to the Health indicators (2005– 2006). The Ministry of Health of Saudi Arabia details the high birth rate despite the dramatic progress in health care in the last 3 decades (Ministry of Health of Saudi Arabia, 2005). The child mortality rate was 20 per 1000 children in 2006 (World Health Organization [WHO], n.d.).The World Factbook Saudi Arabia Central Intelligence Agency (2009) defines that other factors have left Saudi Arabia a country where only 70% of females are literate [8]. According to the WHO (2009) report, in comparison, Sweden had an estimated child mortality rate of 4 per 1000 children in 2005(WHO, 2009).

2.4. Religion and social norms

Islam is the principal religion of most Middle Eastern and North African (MENA) countries, including Saudi Arabia. It shapes and influences individuals socially, traditionally, and culturally and religiously. Based on Islamic rules, sexual conduct should only be practised within marriage(El-Kak, 2013). Ege E, Akin B, Can RK, and Arioiz A.(2011) quote the study of Abdul-Aziz among Egyptian and Jordanian women living in Qatar. Interestingly, 74.4 per cent of Egyptian women and 54.6 per cent of Jordanian women were knowledgeable of and familiar with masturbation despite it being against Islamic teaching.

Manal I Farih (2017) discussed in her article that identifying the perceptions and attitudes of Saudi females regarding issues related to sexuality and Reproductive Health has been engaging and focused directly on women's Reproductive health and Reproductive Rights attitudes (Farih, 2017).

Metz HC. (1992). Discussed that women's rights and freedoms are contingent upon religion, social rules and taboos. The concepts of chastity and sexual modesty have significant implications for gender

roles (Metz, 1992). Researchers state that these fundamental principles are primarily associated with women and comprise the central constructs of ever-important family honour and religious obligation. Modesty is a concept that is significantly emphasized in the Holy Quran for adoption by women and, to a lesser extent, by men, as women are held responsible for fitnah (temptation). This attitude has long been held in the Middle East, taking current religious significance from interpretations of Islamic theology.

Human Rights Watch (2016) reveals that in Saudi Arabia, women are treated as the wards of their fathers, husbands, or next-of-kin male relatives, including their sons, under an institutionalized male guardianship system (Human Rights Watch, 2016).

2.5. Antenatal care

The problems of maternal health in Saudi Arabia are multifactorial, as El-Gilany and El-Wehady (2009) point out in their analysis of antenatal care in Al – the Hasan region. Cultural practices of the country, like polygyny, consanguineous and early marriages, along with fertility patterns of the Saudi society that are un-spaced pregnancies and pregnancies at early or late ages, create medical complications. Hence, the availability of services is not the problem, but the choice and practice of the individual is an issue.

Recent studies have illustrated that attendance at antenatal clinics (ANCs) and receipt of professional perinatal care are associated with reduced maternal deaths (Chavane et al., 2014). ANC reduces maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality directly through the early detection and treatment of pregnancy-related illnesses and indirectly through the identification of women who are at increased risk of complications during childbirth (Sadat-Ali et al., 2004).

2.6. Studies related to family planning services

An additional burden on Saudi Arabian women is the high fertility rate. It has led to a high prevalence of low bone density and osteoporosis among postmenopausal Saudis. High fertility is encouraged by society and government health policy. Like abortion, female permanent sterilization is permitted under only very restricted circumstances, and both potential parents must agree (Al-Kasimi, 2003). Article 16 (1) (e) of the Women's Convention requires state parties to ensure that women

enjoy "rights to decide freely and responsibly on the number and spacing of their children and to have access to the information, education and means to enable them to exercise these rights" (United Nations Entity for Gender Equality and Empowerment of Women, n.d.)

The Cairo International Conference on Population and Development (ICPD, 1994) acknowledged the importance of family planning in promoting women's overall health and reproductive life. Ahmed, Qingfeng et al. found in a Global Analysis of 172 countries using the WHO data that family planning can help reduce maternal mortality by 44 per cent (Ahmed, Li, Liu, & Tsui, 2012). Fear of side effects was found to be one of the major women's concerns for the use of contraceptives in several studies as an essential reason to stop using contraceptives (Darroch, Sedgh, & Ball, 2011). The number of living children was significantly associated with a study in Cameron, which found that women with more children must postpone or limit the number of children, indicating an unmet need (Ajong et al., 2016).

2.7. Government healthcare facilities

In Saudi Arabia, health indicators reveal an overall better performance compared to neighbouring countries' health systems but not to countries with similar economies. However, challenges of access, timeliness, and quality of services are well documented. The 10-year strategy of MOH (2009-19) acknowledged the existence of several healthcare challenges (Council of Ministers Resolution No. 320 September 7, 2009).

Financing was the main challenge for recruitment, training, expansion, and modernization of services. As a percentage of total gross domestic product, Saudi Arabia's health expenditure has remained constant at about 7 per cent, much less than other countries with similar health systems and economies, such as France at 11 per cent or Germany at 10.6 per cent, despite growing health demands (Bradley, Schwandt, & Khan, 2009).

Weak implementation of operational procedures to monitor and improve performance is another challenge addressed through accreditation and licensing. The problem of limited funding is compounded by inefficient utilization of resources, which affects the utility and availability of health care in different regions of Saudi Arabia. In addition, limitations in the health information system affect health research, monitoring, and

planning of services. The MOH strategy also recognized the weaknesses in health infrastructure, emergency and referral services, and preventive care (Ministry of Health of Saudi Arabia, 2016a).

2.8. Rights and violence

To date, no official statistics are available on the consequence of women's health of guardians' refusal to allow care from other than same-sex providers. Of the cases attended by the Saudi Red Crescent, male guardians refused the administration of care in 6 per cent, mostly in remote and conservative areas. The spokesperson for the Red Crescent declared that paramedics follow guardians' wishes if the woman's case is not serious; otherwise, they involve the police but only to document the incident. Moreover, men, while tending to women's family members, frequently subject paramedics to assaults. The Royal Advisory Council, or Shura Council, supported a recommendation by a woman member to criminalize those who obstruct the delivery of emergency care for women by paramedics. However, no official regulation regarding the obstruction of emergency services to women has been instituted regardless of a guardian's permission (Ministry of Health of Saudi Arabia, 2016b).

Gendered policies are attributed to societal norms, which influence the roles and privileges assigned to men and women. Gender norms are constantly constructed and reproduced at different levels, including households, communities, state institutions, or within the health care and legal systems. Violence and coercion are often used to enforce gender norms and, therefore, place the well-being of girls and women at risk (Al-Nayer, 2014). One of the most serious consequences of the vast authority granted to male guardians over women is violence against women and girls. The problem represents a significant public health concern, with a wide array of adverse physical and mental health outcomes. Gender norms such as male control of wealth and decision-making in the family, isolation of women and family, control of a woman's mobility, and acceptance of the use of violence to resolve conflicts are strongly associated with the risk that such violence will occur. In addition, inadequate resources to support survivors of violence and weak legal measures to deter perpetrators contribute to underreporting and proliferation of domestic violence.¹⁸ Social and

legal restrictions on divorce and child custody in Saudi Arabia may also deter women from reporting violence (Keleber, 2010).

Violence against women is common everywhere. In a recent study of 10 countries, more than 1 of every 10 women and up to about 7 of every 10 women reported that they had experienced physical or sexual violence in their lifetimes. Physical violence includes a wide range of behaviours, including hitting, slapping, kicking and beating. Sexual violence includes unwanted sexual contact or attention, coercive sex, and forced sex (rape). Women who experience violence have special health needs, many of them related to sexual and reproductive health. Violence can lead to a range of health problems, including HIV, decreased sexual desire, pain during sex, and chronic pelvic pain. For some women, violence may start or become worse during pregnancy, placing their fetus at risk as well (a Global Handbook for Family Planning, WHO, John Hopkins School)

Access to comprehensive sexual and reproductive health and rights is a basic human right. Women and girls around the world, especially those living in poverty, face restricted or no access to information and services about their reproductive health and rights (www.globalfundforwomen.org).

Need and Objectives of the Study

This study becomes essential when the Saudi Government is determined to give rights to women in various socio-economic spheres of life and make Saudi Women emancipated and empowered. It is envisaged that the study would open a debate and research on the reproductive health, rights and choices of women in Saudi Arabia.

The main objectives of the study are the following.

- ❖ The current status of reproductive health facilities provided by the Government to native and expatriate women in Saudi Arabia.
- ❖ Reproductive rights of native and expatriate women from a Gynecologist's perspective.
- ❖ Reproductive rights of expatriate women in Saudi Arabia from their perspective.

- ❖ Role of religion, education and awareness programmes in the availability, accessibility, and affordability of reproductive health and reproductive rights by native and expatriate women in Saudi Arabia
- ❖ To determine access and utilization of government health facilities by expatriate women.
- ❖ To assess the quality of ANC women in Saudi Arabia received.

3. Sample Size and Data Collection

The present study is exploratory research and employs a combination of qualitative and quantitative research methods for data collection and analysis. The study targeted two distinct participant groups: expatriate Indian women and Saudi gynecologists. To offer a thorough understanding of the topic data on Saudi and Indian expatriate women were collected using two different but complementary approaches.

3.1. Sample size and participant criteria

A total of 50 expatriate women and 35 gynecologists participated in the study. The sample size for expatriate women was calculated using an estimated 46% rate for childbearing women visiting healthcare facilities. Eligible participants included married women of reproductive age (15–49 years) who had resided in Saudi Arabia for at least two years and had at least one child aged two years or younger. Pregnant women and those unwilling to participate were excluded.

Systematic selection was used to enroll participants. Women were identified as those who visited India and were willing to respond via mail or telephone. Participants were randomly chosen during the study period until the sample size was met. All participants were provided a clear explanation of the study's objectives and procedures before beginning the questionnaire-based interview.

3.2. Data collection methods

Data is gathered through face-to-face interviews, telephonic conversations, and email correspondence using a standardized, paper-based questionnaire. The questionnaire was piloted beforehand to ensure its consistency and validity.

For expatriate Indian women, the questionnaire addressed various aspects of reproductive healthcare utilization, including antenatal and postnatal care, health facility delivery, skilled attendance during delivery, family planning, women's rights, and awareness of government healthcare schemes. Participants were asked specific questions, such as whether they received at least four skilled antenatal checkups, the place of delivery, the presence of a qualified healthcare provider during delivery, and modern family planning methods. These responses were analyzed using socio-demographic factors (e.g., age, education, occupation, and residency) and obstetric factors (e.g., number of deliveries and women's decision-making rights).

For Saudi gynecologists, in-depth interviews were conducted to explore their perspectives on reproductive health issues faced by Saudi women. The same questionnaire themes were adapted for gynecologists, and their professional observations provided a comparative understanding of healthcare practices in Saudi Arabia.

3.3. Analysis and case study development

Data from expatriate women and gynecologists were systematically analyzed. Responses were correlated with socio-demographic and obstetric factors to identify patterns affecting the utilization of reproductive healthcare services. Insights from gynecologists were synthesized into case studies to complement the quantitative findings and provide a holistic understanding of the research questions.

This dual approach ensured that individual experiences and professional healthcare perspectives were integrated, leading to robust and actionable findings.

4. Results and Discussion

Expatriate Indian women in Saudi Arabia are interviewed regarding their demographic profile, Health Services Utilisation for Antenatal care/Postnatal care/Family planning Services, and Health Services Utilisation: Preferences for Child Delivery. The following tables and analyses provide a comprehensive picture of the reproductive health and rights of Expatriate Indian women.

Table1: Demographic Characteristics of Indian Expatriate Respondents (n=50)

Characteristics	Number of Respondents	%
Age of women(years)		
15-24	04	8
25-34	17	34
35-49	29	58
Work Status		
Housewife/Not Working	38	76
Employed	12	24
Education Level		
Illiterate	00	00
Able to read and write	00	00
Primary Secondary	07	14
Graduate and above	43	86
Number of Children		
01	03	06
02-04	47	44
≥5	00	00

Table 1 provides demographic and socio-economic characteristics of the respondents, offering insights into their age, work status, education level, and number of children. Below is the analysis of each demographic characteristic:

Age distribution: Most respondents (58%) fall into the 35–49 age group, indicating a higher representation of women in the older reproductive age range. The 25–34 age group comprises 34% of respondents, while only 8% are from the youngest age group, 15–24 years. This skewed age distribution suggests the study broadly captures the experiences of older women, who are likely to have more experience with reproductive health services and family planning.

Work status: A significant proportion of the respondents (76%) are homemakers or not working, while 24% are employed. This indicates that most participants are likely to rely on family income or spousal support, which could influence their access to and utilization of healthcare services.

Education level: A striking 86% of respondents are graduates or have higher education, while 14% have primary or secondary education. None of the participants were illiterate or had only basic literacy skills. This high level of education among respondents may reflect a subset of the expatriate population that prioritizes education, potentially contributing to better awareness of healthcare options and higher utilization of services.

Number of children: Most respondents (94%) have 2–4 children, with only 6% having one child. None of the respondents reported having five or more children. This distribution indicates that most respondents are within family sizes typically seen in modern contexts, which might reflect a trend toward smaller families among expatriate communities.

Therefore, The data shows a predominantly educated and non-working group of older women (35–49 years) with moderate family sizes (2–4 children). This demographic likely has a relatively stable socio-economic background, with education playing a pivotal role in healthcare decision-making and access. The lack of illiterate or minimally educated respondents might limit insights into the experiences of less-educated women, possibly skewing the findings toward a more advantaged subgroup. The significant implications are that the high education level and moderate family sizes better understand healthcare and family planning services, potentially leading to positive outcomes in reproductive health.

Table 2. Health Services Utilisation for Antenatal care/Postnatal care/Family planning Services

Characteristics	Number	%
Seeking antenatal care		
Yes	50	100
No	00	00
Number of antenatal visits		
<4	11	22
≥4	39	78
Received tetanus vaccine?		
Yes	50	100
No	00	00
Received education about danger signs in pregnancy?		
Yes	37	74
No	13	26
Site for seeking antenatal care		
Public primary healthcare center	03	06
Public Hospital's Clinic	08	16
Private Clinic/Hospital	39	78
Source of encouragement for seeking antenatal care		
Husband	33	66

Health facility workers	00	00
Relatives	09	18
Self-Initiative	08	16
Seeking postnatal care		
Yes	34	68
No	16	32
Seeking Family Planning Services		
Yes	43	86
No	07	14

The data (Table 2) reveals essential information about the respondents' use of family planning services, postnatal care (PNC), and prenatal care (ANC). Every participant (100%) sought prenatal treatment, indicating that everyone understood its importance. Nevertheless, 22% had fewer ANC visits, even though 78% followed the suggested four or more appointments, suggesting potential obstacles, including follow-up or poor accessibility. The 100% universal tetanus vaccine coverage demonstrates how well immunization campaigns reach their target demographic.

Only 74% of respondents were aware of the warning symptoms of pregnancy, indicating a lack of health education despite the widespread use of ANC. This highlights the need for improved educational interventions because it leaves 26% potentially unprepared for catastrophes. 78% of respondents said they preferred private clinics or hospitals regarding healthcare facilities, whereas 16% went to public hospital clinics, and 6% relied on public primary healthcare centres. Perceptions of better accessibility or higher quality care may be the reason for this preference for private institutions. Still, it also emphasizes enhancing public healthcare services to address these differences.

Husbands were the primary source of encouragement for obtaining ANC (66%), followed by family members (18%) and self-motivation (16%). There is a need for improvement in community outreach and healthcare

professional engagement in improving maternal health, as seen by the noteworthy lack of influence from health facility employees.

Only 68% of respondents sought postnatal care (PNC), which is less common than ANC. This disparity emphasizes the need for increased knowledge and availability of postpartum services, which are critical to the health of mothers and newborns. However, 86% of respondents used family planning services, suggesting that reproductive health awareness is rising. However, obstacles, including cultural opposition, ignorance, or restricted access to contraception, may have prevented the remaining 14% from using these services.

Overall, the evidence indicates inequalities in education and postpartum service utilisation, a heavy reliance on private healthcare facilities, and considerable familial influence (especially from spouses) when seeking care. Targeted health education campaigns, better public healthcare accessibility and quality, and increased participation of male family members in maternal health programs are all necessary to address these problems. Improving overall maternal and reproductive health outcomes also requires increasing outreach for postnatal care and guaranteeing fair access to family planning options.

Table 3. Health Services Utilisation: Preferences for Child Delivery

Characteristics	Number	%
Preferred site of delivery		
Home	00	00
Healthcare facility	50	100
Reasons for home delivery preference(n=00)		
Privacy	00	00
Low Cost	00	00
Low trust in healthcare facilities	00	00
Reasons in healthcare facilities preference(n=50)		
Complications in previous	00	00

delivery		
Better healthcare provision	37	74
Experienced physician	13	26
Complication during previous pregnancy	00	00
Others	00	00

Table 3 denotes that all respondents (100%) chose institutional delivery, indicating a widespread preference for healthcare facilities as the delivery place. This tendency demonstrates a keen understanding of the advantages of giving birth at a medical facility and illustrates how easily accessible and well-liked these facilities are in the neighbourhood. Interestingly, there were no home birth instances, suggesting institutional care supplanted traditional methods.

74% of respondents said that "better healthcare provision" was the main factor in their decision to use a particular healthcare facility. In comparison, 26% said that the presence of skilled doctors was a deciding factor. These findings highlight excellent quality and dependability in institutional settings. The lack of home delivery services and inclinations for home-related elements like affordability or privacy indicate that this demographic has successfully mitigated barriers like financial constraints or distrust in healthcare systems.

It is interesting to note that none of the respondents said their selection was affected by issues from prior pregnancies or births. This could indicate that the research participants had a comparatively low rate of high-risk pregnancies or that other considerations, including the general standard of care, influenced their choice more strongly.

One encouraging trend that shows the effectiveness of public health initiatives to promote safer birthing practices is the widespread reliance on institutional delivery. Healthcare systems must prioritise quality enhancements in maternal care services to preserve this success, especially by guaranteeing the availability of qualified doctors and upholding high standards of care. To overcome any lingering financial or cultural obstacles, officials should also duplicate this achievement in other areas or demographic groups where home deliveries are still

common. Improving these programs will improve the health of mothers and new-borns even more.

Expatriate Women's Views

Indian expatriate women interviewed for the study were predominantly educated. Following is the narration regarding reproductive health and rights scenario while living in Saudi Arabia.

In Saudi Arabia, the expats keep to themselves and do not mingle with the locals. Apart from the workplaces in the public and private departments, they do not interact with the Saudis much and have no social gathering together. These expats follow their country's culture and practices, such as having only two or three children, spacing in between, family planning, other birth-related rituals, festive activities, etc.

Many expatriate ladies are working in the educational and medical sectors. When a woman gets a job in Saudi, they have to travel and stay either with their husband or father, a mahram, as per the law. But now, some changes in restrictions regarding going out with mahram can only be seen. Non-working females are attached to their husband's medical benefits.

They go to Private health clinics and hospitals with the best medical facilities. Treated are respectfully in maternity health care centres. Health providers advise them about their diet, exercise, tests, and medications. Family planning workshops are also organized in the hospitals, where these women are given multiple choices to choose from and adapt the family planning options after the delivery. They are also educated in family planning and made aware of the side effects of the different methods. Unlike the locals, these females have the right to choose and decide the best for them. More importance is given to ANC's (ante-natal care) than PNC's (post-natal care), as is the general practice back home insured.

Gynecologist's Perspective on Saudi Women's Reproductive Health

The study used the knowledge of gynecologists in Saudi hospitals to gather information about the reproductive health of Saudi women. Structured interviews with Saudi gynecologists were used to gather data, emphasising their experiences treating Saudi women and their professional insights. The narration through Gynecologists abreast our understanding regarding Saudi women's reproductive health and rights choices.

There has been a drastic change in healthcare and education in Saudi Arabia since 1980. In the early 80s, barely 60 to 70% of girls received primary education, reaching at least the 10th grade. The credit goes to King Faisal's wife, who worked towards girl's education in a big way. The Government, to provide the best possible education to the girls, absolutely free, has established various colleges and Universities. Scholarships are also provided for higher education abroad, with expenses covered by one guardian (mehram) to accompany the girl. This development in education has directly affected the health care of girls and women due to overall awareness and attitude towards health needs. There is no concept of co-education in the Kingdom and, therefore, no intermingling among the genders in early and adolescent age. This gives rise to many misconceptions in the young minds towards opposite sexes. In the 80s, 40% of the deliveries were at home due to backwardness, poor education and unawareness towards reproductive health. 90% of the deliveries occur institutionally, as awareness has risen steeply over the years. In the early 80s, a mother would give 6 to 7 births and more without any gap in between, and of course, family planning was taboo. Presently, the number has come down to 4 to 5 births, even less, with considerable gaps in between—many practice family planning. Oral contraceptive pills and other contraceptive materials are available at all health centres, free of cost.

At the primary health care and health service centres, education about reproductive health, pre-and post-natal care, etc., is imparted through workshops and counselling programs. The importance of regular checkups, a balanced diet, good hygiene, prescribed spacing between two deliveries, proper medication and intake of tablets of iron, folic acid, calcium, other minerals and vitamins, etc. and breastfeeding is taught by the health care providers. Moreover, emphasis is placed on understanding the benefits of institutional deliveries. Home health educators are provided by various hospitals as well.

The primary health care centres are situated at vast distances in urban areas. All Saudi families are registered at the primary health centres, where all pregnancy tests are done for free. Vaccinations are also done in these centres, and the life expectancy of the local women and children has increased considerably due to these vaccinations. Almost all women get tetanus doses at the time of pregnancy. Many Saudi Women had four or more antenatal care visits to the healthcare facilities during the pregnancy. They received the anti-tetanus vaccine during their antenatal visits and information on the danger signs in pregnancy. The most common site visited by the respondents seeking

antenatal care was the public healthcare centres. Post-natal care visits to healthcare facilities are also common practice in Saudi women. They had received Family Planning advice during their antenatal and post-natal visits.

If a case is untreatable at primary centres, it is referred to secondary health centres or hospitals. Tertiary care centres look after critical instances of women. Government hospitals only treat the local population; no expats are allowed here. The expats have to visit private health clinics. Sometimes, in extreme emergencies, though, expats are also treated at these hospitals.

Co-education does not exist even in medical colleges. In hospital years (fourth and fifth years), the medical students have separate batches for girls and boys. The Saudi female medical teachers do not take classes with male students. Moreover, even if some expatriate female teachers are ready to take classes with male students, the students do not agree to such an arrangement.

Polygamy in the country is a cultural and traditional practice. Either the wealthy and elite classes or families from the lower strata go for it. Religion being at the core of every practice, be it cultural or traditional, polygamy is also undertaken according to Islamic laws. Each wife should be treated on par with the others and have equal rights. Despite all the rights and facilities, male counterparts make all the decisions and have the final say. This holds even in educated families. Though the girls now disapprove and favour this practice of polygamy, they cannot resist or speak against it.

Speaking about the rights of the Saudi women – they have none or negligible. If we talk of the affluent class, these women are as if in a golden cage without any rights as such. The father or the husband are the decision makers for their daughters and wives, and their daughters or wives cannot challenge them.

Conclusion

The findings highlight the significant influence of education, cultural practices, and healthcare policies on women's health outcomes in Saudi Arabia. Key findings are revealed by the study's analysis of Saudi women's healthcare utilisation and sociodemographic trends. Of the 50 respondents, 76% were housewives, 86% were educated (graduates and up), and 58% were between the ages of 35 and 49. 96% of women gave birth to two or four children. 68% of women had four or more prenatal visits, and 66% of women sought postnatal treatment, indicating

significant healthcare utilisation. 74% of respondents were aware of pregnancy danger indicators, and all respondents obtained the anti-tetanus vaccination. 78% of respondents said they preferred private healthcare facilities, and 66% said their husbands urged them to get prenatal care. Due to improved facilities and low-risk management, institutional deliveries became common.

Despite the lack of co-education and gender mixing in Saudi Arabia, gynaecologists highlighted the beneficial effects of education on women's health awareness and attitudes. Saudi citizens have free access to government health facilities, and 90% of births occur in hospitals. With 80% of young Saudi women using family planning, it has become more widely accepted. Birth rates are now between four and five children per woman.

Concerns about social norms like polygamy, healthcare accessibility, and marriage age are still present. Lower socioeconomic levels and the wealthy elite are the main groups that engage in polygamy. Government hospitals are inaccessible to expatriates. These results highlight how healthcare regulations, cultural customs, and education shape Saudi Arabian women's health outcomes.

Limitations

Our findings are interpreted in light of the Saudi culture and society governed by Islamic Sharia law. This study has limitations as some expatriate women were interviewed online and on the telephone, and some were face-to-face when visiting India.

This paper reveals vast gaps between local and expatriate women regarding essential women's health rights. Finally, this study presents recommendations for health policy planners in Saudi Arabia to reduce the negative influence of gender norms on women's health and that there should be no discrimination in health services for expatriates because health is the basic need and requirement of all human beings.

Efforts should also focus on increasing awareness about the importance of prenatal and post-natal care, encouraging institutional deliveries in government hospitals, and addressing fears or inhibitions surrounding such facilities. Further research is recommended to explore Saudi women's reproductive health, rights, and sexual attitudes across the country to inform comprehensive health policies.

Disclaimer

The author alone is responsible for the views expressed in this article and do not necessarily represent the views, decisions or policies of the institutions with which she is affiliated.

Conflicts of Interest

The author has no conflicts of interest.

Declarations

Consent to participate

Informed written consent was obtained from all participants in interviews.

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Reproductive Health and Rights of Women in Saudi Arabia - Fazli

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